

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

EMOTIONAL STATE OF POLICE OFFICERS

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Abstract

This paper aims to understand the relationship between well-being and emotional state among police officers. The author examines whether the condition is the causes of any emotional problem among police officers. The study focuses on the relationship between emotional problems and condition factor, using different literature materials.

Different studies refer the influence of individual characteristics on the experience of stressors among police officers, and consequently the experience of burnout among this population (Alarcon, Eschleman & Bowling, 2009; Ivie & Garland, 2011; Swider & Zimmermann, 2010; Vuorensyrja & Malkia, 2011). Additionally, police job condition, circumstances and emotional problems have influence on the physical and mental health of the police officer, such as depression, aggressive behaviours and suicide (Blum, 2000; Violanti, 1996). Previous research investigating the causes of burnout has mainly concentrated on the reasons of burnout such as work criteria or organisational or social influences (Bühler & Land, 2003). Majority of the previous studies have been conducted analysing personality and individual characteristics of police officers (Abrahamsen & Strype, 2010; Burbeck & Furnham, 1984; Detrick & Chibnall, 2013; Goldstein, 1968; Hennessy, 1999; Twersky-Glasner, 2005).

Considering that police officers have a stressful job condition that can elicit burnout and the fact that stressful situations lead to a different mental health issues. It is believed that the findings will contribute not only to the theoretical understanding of the burnout concept, but will also include implications for practitioners in the area.

The Maslach Burnout Inventory was used to measure burnout, and case study collected data from 10 male police officers. Data was collected from Azerbaijan male police officers, are being treated in the Hospital. Participants were aged between 28 and 52 years ($M=36.3$ and $SD=7.7$), with high level of education. Concerning marital status, 86% were married, and 74% have children. Work experience ranged between 2 and 24 years ($M=7.9$ and $SD=2.3$). A self-completed, anonymous and confidential questionnaire was filled in after formal authorisation.

This study has some limitations. Firstly, the case study was used to analyze the effect of job condition and burnout problem. For this purpose, longitudinal studies are needed. Secondly, the limited number of the police officers have participated, so the big population of the police population needs further investigation. The next limitation is related to their job condition, only officers who are working in the capital were involved to the research.

Keywords: emotional problems, mental health of police officers, well-being, interpersonal relationship.

Literature review: Among the problems recorded in the mental health of police officers, the emotional problem, and emotional burnout is specially mentioned. A number of researchers have associated this problem with difficulties in working hours, work routines, and recorded interpersonal relationships. It has been reflected in the work of a number of researchers that police officers regularly work under stress and have uncertain working conditions (Blum, 2000; Brown & Campbell, 1994; Oligny, 1991; Ransley & Mazerolle, 2009).

Also, in their research, Stone and colleagues investigated that working conditions increase the symptoms of stress in police officers (Stone, 2004). In another study, between 1988 and 2005, various professions was investigated as the stressful event and the police profession was identified as the 2nd stressful profession (Gonzalves & Neves, 2010; Johnson et al., 2005). Also, the image created by this profession among people, their use of weapons also play a role in the emergence of this stress (Brown & Campbell, 1994; Hackett & Violanti, 2003; Selye, 1978; Turvey, 1995).

The problem of stress and burnout in police officers began to be studied after the 1990s more effectively.

Australia (Ransley vø Mazerolle, 2009), USA (Goodman, 1990; Hassell, Archbold & Stichman, 2011; Menard & Arter, 2013), Canada (Le Blanc, Regehr, Jelley & Bareth, 2008; Oligny, 1991), Tailand (Chen, 2009; Chueh, Yen, Lu & Yang, 2011), Israel (Pines & Keinan, 2006), Africa (Agolla, 2009; Storm & Rothmann, 2003), India (Bawa & Kaur, 2011; Ranta & Sud, 2008), Brazil (Coleta & Coleta, 2008; Soares et al., 2012), Europe in the Netherlands (Euwema, Kop & Bakker, 2004; Velden, Kleber, Grievink & Yzermans, 2010), Switzerland (Gerber, Hartmann, Brand, Holsboer-Trachsler & Pöhse, 2010), Finland (Vuorensyrja & Malkia, 2011), Norvey (Langballe, Innstrand, Hagtvet, Falkum & Aasland, 2009), Lithuania (Bandeževiciene, Birbilaite & Dirzyte, 2010), Turkey (Azizoglu & Ozyer, 2010), Italy (Pancheri et al., 2002), Spain (Durón, Montalbón & Stangeland, 2006; Gil-Monte, 2002; Ravelo, Garcia & Dorta, 2009), and Portugal (Durro, 2010, 2011; Gonzalves & Neves, 2010; Manuel & Soeiro, 2010; Queirys & Marques, 2013; Recasens i Brunet, Basanta, Agra, Queirys & Selmini, 2009) a lot of researchers and authors investigate this problem. Despite the ethnic and cultural differences between the countries, the indicators related to stress,

burnout, physical problems, aggressive behavior and suicide were similar to each other. Factors causing stress include fear, workload, insufficient support related to professional activity (Kop, Euwema & Schaufeli, 1999; Page & Jacobs, 2011; Ravelo et al., 2009; Violanti, 1999), inability to express emotions and feelings. (Le Blanc et al., 2008; van Gelderen, Bakker, Konijn & Demerouti, 2011), conflict between job demands and job opportunities (Euwema et al., 2004), coping skills (Pancheri et al., 2002), low pay (Pines & Keinan 2006), the public image of the police (Agolla, 2009; Wu, 2009) has been particularly emphasized.

What is emotional burnout? - The main characteristics of emotional burnout include loss of energy, lack of motivation, negative attitude towards others and active withdrawal from others. Burnout is examined with measures of emotional exhaustion, disengagement, and personal accomplishment. Emotional exhaustion is feeling emotionally overloaded and exhausted due to the work done by a person and is the most important symptom of burnout syndrome. Individual lack of success is defined as not being able to cope with the problem successfully and seeing oneself as insufficient. The individual's motivation towards work is low, he feels lack of control and helplessness. Exhaustion in the individual is manifested by an increase in neglect with emotional exhaustion, a decrease in personal success and a sense of success.

Burnout syndrome is expressed in 4 stages. This classification provides a worldview that makes it easier to understand emotional burnout. But in fact, burnout is not a process in which a person passes from one stage to another, but a continuous fact.

The first stage - the stage of excitement and enthusiasm: In this stage, a high level of optimism, an increase in energy and professional expectations that reach unrealistic dimensions are exhibited. trying to adapt.

The second stage - Stagnation stage: In this stage, there is already a certain decrease in desire and hope. Person begins to worry about the difficulties he encountered while practicing his profession, some points he treated as unimportant before. He cannot do anything in addition to the required work. Because his profession is theoretical and cannot fully encompass human existence in all its practical aspects.

The third stage - Obstacle stage: The person who started working to help and serve other people, understands how difficult it is to change people, system, negative working conditions. He experiences a constant feeling of obstruction. At this point, one of 3 ways is chosen. These include activating adaptive defenses and coping strategies, inciting emotional burnout with maladaptive defenses and coping strategies, withdrawing from the situation, or giving up.

The fourth stage - the stage of indifference (Apathy-slowness): In this stage, a very deep emotional disconnection, a deep disbelief and hopelessness are observed. He continues his profession for economic and social security, he does not enjoy it. In such a situation, work life is a satisfaction for the individual and rather than being a field of self-realization, it will be a field that only gives a person difficulty and unhappiness.

The main criteria that will appear in the case of emotional burnout in a person are the following:

Psychophysiological symptoms: feeling of fatigue and exhaustion, loss of energy, chronic feeling of coldness, chronic headaches and sleep disorders, gastrointestinal disorders and weight loss, breathing difficulties, psychosomatic diseases, increased coronary heart disease density.

Psychological symptoms: emotional exhaustion, chronic irritability, irritability, occasional cognitive difficulties, delusions, low mood, anxiety, impatience, low self-esteem, worthlessness, hypersensitivity to criticism, lack of decision-making, lethargy, emptiness and sense of meaninglessness, hopelessness.

Behavioral symptoms: making mistakes, coming to work late, not coming to work without permission or due to illness, tendency to miss work, impairment in service quality, impairment in work and non-work relationships, increase in accidents and injuries, loss of interest in the company.

Reasons of emotional burnout: When looking at the research done on this topic, while the first experimental works are directly related to personality, the works done in recent years are generally focused on emotional burnout caused by organizational factors. Another view on this topic is that both organizational and individual problems cause this syndrome and that burnout is a multidimensional complex phenomenon.

Burnout syndrome, in a different form, is more often observed in people who are much more excited and eager when they start work. This situation is attributed by experts to the fact that those people are exhausted in a short time by using more energy with their first excitement. 3 situations that are very effective in the formation of emotional burnout syndrome are noted:

Role conflict: A person with conflicting responsibilities tries to do everything at the same level instead of prioritizing his responsibilities. In this case, after a certain period of time, fatigue occurs and the result is burnout syndrome.

Role Ambiguity: The employee knows that he is expected to paint a good career portrait, but he is not sure how to do it since he has no role model.

Overburdened: A person burdened with too many responsibilities without saying "no" to anyone eventually reaches the point of exhaustion.

Research participants and methods: The research was conducted in 2023 with police officers working in the junior chief staff of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Azerbaijan. The method of research- Maslach questionnaire was applied with the main purpose of the study - measuring the burnout syndrome in police officers. Each participant was informed in advance that participation in the study was voluntary and that the results were confidential.

Limitations of the study: The following limitations were noted during the study. 1) the participants are only men; 2) the number of participants is limited; 3) participants work only in Baku. Based on these limitations, it is recommended to continue the study with a larger number of participants in later stages.

Results: During the study, the sociodemographic indicators of the participants - age, years of service (experience) and marital status were recorded as independent variables; burnout syndrome indicators and

Maslach questionnaire results were monitored as dependent variables. Maslach survey results were calculated in the following form:

Table 1.

Maslach inventory result interpretation

Section A - indicators of general fatigue, exhaustion	<15 score- low level of burnout	16-24 score – medium level of burnout	>25 score- high level of burnout
Section B – depersonalization and decreased empathy	<5 score – low level	6-10 score – medium level	>11 score- high level
Section C – personal achievement	<30 score – high level of burnout	31-36 score – medium level	>37 score- low level of burnout

The age limit of the participants varied from 28 to 52 years, and their years of service varied from 2 to 24 years.

Section I indicators of general fatigue, burnout; min. 0, max. 47; average score was 24.7. Results ranged from a low to high threshold for emotional exhaustion.

Section II indicators of depersonalization and decreased empathy min.2, max.15; average score was 10.6 points. Although the results varied between the

lower and upper limits, the upper limit was more dominant.

Section III personal achievement indicators were min. 27, max. 45, the average was 37.6 points.

Looking at the relationship between participants' age and emotional exhaustion, no statistically significant relationship was found between the results. Indicators of emotional exhaustion at different ages are distributed differently.

Graph 1. Distribution of results by age factor

Looking at the relationship between the participants' years of service and their emotional exhaustion indicators, it was found that the indicators were distributed differently for different years. However, the indicators of depersonalization and empathy decrease in

section II began to rise gradually as the length of service increased, and this index did not change with a significant difference.

Graph 2. Distribution of results by years of service (experience) factor

When the participants were divided into two condition groups as married and single and look at the relationship between emotional exhaustion and the family factor, the indicator of single and married people is collected in the table below.

Table 2.

Distribution of indicators of emotional exhaustion by family factor

Family factor	Section I	Section II	Section III
single	25	7	29
married	24,6	11,5	39,7

As shown in the table, no significant difference was found in section I, but in sections II and III, the indicators of married persons were higher than those of singles.

The police officers expressed their emotional state as the following statements:

"Long working hours prevent me from spending enough time with my family. We can't do anything. We cannot fulfill the wishes of our family. It makes me very sad."

"In return for our work, our low wages reduce our motivation towards work. We love our work, we only suffer financially."

"mostly additional tasks and extended working hours tire us. We don't have enough time to rest. We cannot fulfill our duties towards our family. "

"We do our work with pride. But sometimes we can get serious punishments for very small mistakes. Sometimes people want to be appreciated for their work. But we remain out of attention."

Based on their speech the main reason for emotional problems among police officers is the heavy work schedule, working under constant stress and long working hours. Long working hours increase their internal objections because they cannot devote enough time to their families, personal development, and social life. Also, the police profession creates difficulties for them to cope with their responsibilities as an individual in terms of time. In addition, lack of specific job duties and high expectations, harshness of punishments, etc.

Some reasons can lead to emotional exhaustion. In the face of such difficulties, they note that the police officers are not sufficiently provided financially, and in the face of these difficulties, their motivation decreases. In addition to insufficient financial support, police officers complain that their work is not valued by the management, they are neglected by them, and they mention it as the reason for their low motivation.

Conclusion and recommendations: This article, which focuses on the study of emotional state and burnout among police officers, is based on a literature review and a small case study. During the study, the age, experience years and marital status of police officers were determined as independent variables, and the indicators of emotional exhaustion based on the Maslach survey were determined as dependent variables. Also, an analysis was conducted on the individual samples of each participant using the case study method. Based on the results of the study, analysis of the literature, and also the limited aspects of the study, the following recommendations are made:

- In order to prevent cases of emotional exhaustion and decreased empathy in the mental health of police officers, awareness-raising activities should be carried out regularly;

- Additional rest hours and other opportunities should be created for employees working in difficult situations, information should be provided to increase their appeal to psychological services and receive timely psychological support;

- Research in this direction should be conducted with a wider group of participants and the results analyzed; the obtained results are reported to the management within the framework of ethical rules, preparation of measures and giving proposals can give more effective results.

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